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San Vicente, Tarlac City, Philippines, 2500

pinagpalapublishingservices@gmail.com

+639985799958

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The Seeds and the Blue Seas

CHIQUI D. MALABANAN, MAED

TEACHER III

TAAL CENTRAL SCHOOL

BATANGAS, REGION IV-ACALABARZON, PHILIPPINES

It was still dark outside when Pina, a giant, woke up excitedly to get out of the cave. She ran to the coast to watch the astonishing scene of the sunrise. What makes this morning unique? It was the day that his father let her accompany him in his travels to the seas. She was always looking forward to this day. She can meet new children like her, while her father, who is a farmer, trades seeds of plants and crops.

Pina rushed back to the cave and excitedly woke up her father. Her father got up from his sleep and greeted her good morning. "Prepare your things, it's going to be a long and tiring travel", her father commanded. Pina immediately picked up her basket and started packing her things. Her father reminded her that the basket of seeds, most importantly, should not be forgotten. "Pina, it will take days to go to the southeast. It's a magnificent place with the bluest waters, however, it can be dangerous. I'll be the happiest when we both go home safe." her father said in a serious tone followed by a kiss on her forehead. Pina's mind was stuck on the thought of the blue waters, she wondered how beautiful it might be when they got there. She snapped out of her daydream when her father said "Pina, don't forget the seeds. Can you please help me carry them?". With all the excitement, Pina replied "No problem, Papa. I carry one, and you carry three. I'm your princess anyway". They laughed as they started their journey on foot.

One day, two days, three and a half days had passed, and Pina was still enthusiastically crossing waters. Until finally, her father stopped walking and uttered, "We are here. This is the southeast waters, Pina". Those were the words she has been waiting to hear. Her father was right. It was the bluest waters she had seen. She got mesmerized by the beauty and what seemed a colorful life of fishes and corals it had underneath, but the moment ended when he heard her father scream, "Pina, hurry up!". She looked behind her and there were dark clouds and a heavy storm ready to come. She ran as fast as she could towards her father, running out of breath and strength, but it was all too late when she slipped and all the seed, she was carrying scattered at the sea.

That was the last time Pina's father saw her princess, so he prayed and cried to Bathala, "Ang buhay ko ay may katuturan lamang sa piling ni Pina, sa piling ni Pina!" Many years later, sprinkles of land appeared on the southeast waters, and is later called Pilipinas.

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